

Poetry

A song of partition

Aadishri Yadav

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In anticipation, I wonder still,
Of loss and pain, the cries that chill,
The bloodshed vast o'er lands they called home,
Now deserted, once a haven to roam.

I shudder at visions of trauma's cruel art,
Narrations of anguish, years torn apart.
Imagine an 8-year-old, amidst the strife,
Where bodies fall, a brutal dance of life.

As a child of the new millennium's grace,
I only know tales that leave a scarred trace,
When humanity faltered, veiled in a masquerade,
And trains became blood-stained, a gruesome cascade.

How can I fathom the old times' grace,
When borders were crossed with a mournful embrace?
The fire of power consumes, without heed,
Both those who hide and those who plant the seed.

Chaos knew no bounds, the mob took the stage,
When faith became treason, a world in outrage,
How do I preserve my fragile life,
In an eternal void of fear and strife?

Some chose death, some lived in pain,
The choices were harsh, the scars remain,
British schemes to divide and rule,
Politicians blinded, ambition their fuel.

The state sought to heal, reunite,
The fractured minds, in the pale moonlight,
But many had accepted their fate, embraced their despair,
In 1947, a world in disrepair.

Blessed are those who never saw,
The horrors of that fateful draw,
And those yet unborn, like me,
Who hear the tales from our elders' plea.

May the new world know no such dread,
May political ambitions be guided instead,
Towards unity, not fear's widespread sway,
May lost souls find eternal peace today.

In memory of those who suffered the divide,
Let unity and love forever reside,
Partition took a piece of every soul,
In our hearts, their stories make us whole.

About the Author

Hello readers, my name is Aadishri Yadav. I am a law student. I am no writer, but when I write it comes from my inquisitive thoughts. I try my best to put in what I truly feel. It's usually a gush of a lot of feelings which desperately want to be expressed. I love finding new facts and books to read. I want to immerse myself in art because there is no solace to humans except art.

Sussex Centre for Human Rights Research

Book Launch: 'Black Iconography and Colonial (Re)production at the International Criminal Court: Independence Char Cha' by Dr Stanley Mwangi Wanjiru

Date: Friday 2nd December 2022

Time: 12-2pm

Venue: Freeman F22 and online

Speaker: Dr Sara Kendall (Reader in International Law, University of Kent)

About the book:

This book explores the reproduction of colonialism at the International Criminal Court (ICC) and examines international criminal law (ICL) vs the black body through an immersive format of art, music, poetry, and architecture and post-colonial/critical race theory lens.

Taking a multi-disciplinary approach, the book interrogates the operationalisation of the Rome Statute to detail a Eurocentric hegemony at the core of ICL. It explores how colonialism and slavery have come to shape ICL, exposing the perpetuation of the colonial, and warns that it has ominous contemporary and future implications for Africa. As currently envisaged and acted out at the ICC, this law is founded on deceptive and colonial ideas of 'what is wrong' in/with the world. The book finds that the contemporary ICL regime is founded on white supremacy that corrupts the law's interaction with the African. The African is but a unit utilised by the global elite to exploit and extract resources. From time to time, these alliances disintegrate with ICL becoming a retaliatory tool of choice. What is at stake is power, not justice. This power has been hierarchical with Eurocentrism at the top throughout modern history. Colonialism is seen not to have ended but to have regerminated through the foundation of the 'independent' African state. The ICC reproduces the colonial by use of European law and, ultimately, the over-representation of the black accused. To conclude, the book provides a liberated African forum that can address conflicts in the content, with a call for the end of the ICC's involvement in Africa. The demand is made for an African court that utilises non-colonising African norms which are uniquely suited to address local conflicts.

Multidisciplinary in nature, this book will be of great interest to students and scholars of international criminal law, criminal justice, human rights law, African studies, global social justice, sociology, anthropology, postcolonial studies, and philosophy.